

FAT-SOLUBLE VITAMINS IN THE BODY

N.T. Alimkhodjaeva

Associate Professor of the Department of Medical and Biological Chemistry, Medical Biology,
General Genetics, TashPMI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15161670>

Abstract. *The article discusses fat-soluble vitamins – A, D, E and K, their physiological role, sources, absorption mechanisms and impact on human health. Particular attention is paid to their biochemical properties, function in the body and possible consequences of deficiency or hypervitaminosis. The features of their absorption, transportation and storage, as well as the role of fats in ensuring the bioavailability of these vitamins are also discussed. The article provides recommendations for rational consumption of fat-soluble vitamins, taking into account age and physiological needs.*

Keywords: *fat-soluble vitamins, vitamin A, vitamin D, vitamin E, vitamin K.*

Introduction. There is no strict definition of vitamins in science, there are only necessary characteristics for classifying a substance as a vitamin. A substance that meets the following four characteristics can be recognized as a vitamin:

- organic matter;
- a vital substance, without which the clinical picture of the disease develops;
 - the body does not produce the substance in the required quantity or does not produce it at all;
- the substance is required in minimal quantities (for humans - less than 0.1 g per day, for example, the largest daily recommended dose is vitamin C, and it is equal to 90 mg).

Vitamins perform *a catalytic* function in the active centers of various enzymes, and can also participate in humoral regulation as exogenous prohormones and hormones. Each organism has specific needs for vitamins: a molecule can be a vitamin for one species, but not a vitamin for another species.

The concentration of vitamins in tissues and the daily requirement for them are small, but with insufficient intake of vitamins in the body, characteristic and dangerous pathological changes (diseases) occur, for example, scurvy and pellagra.

Most vitamins are not synthesized in the human body and must be obtained entirely from food. A minority are those synthesized in the body: vitamin D, which is formed in human skin under the influence of ultraviolet light; vitamin A, which can be synthesized from precursors that enter the body with food; and one form of vitamin B3 - niacin, the precursor of which is an amino acid tryptophan. In addition, vitamins K and B₇ are usually synthesized in sufficient quantities by symbiotic bacterial microflora human colon.

A person receives daily norms of vitamins with food with energy expenditure of about 3500 kcal per day. Since people in the modern world move little, they do not need such an amount of food, and vitamin supplements become necessary to obtain the required amount of vitamins. However, in the case of a varied diet, the amount of vitamins in food is sufficient for a healthy person.

Methodology. Vitamins are conventionally designated by letters of the Latin alphabet: A, B, C, D, E, K. It was later discovered that some of them are not independent substances, but a complex of individual vitamins. For example, the B vitamins have been well studied. The names of vitamins have changed as they have been studied. The modern names of vitamins were adopted in 1956 by the Commission on Nomenclature of the Biochemical Section of the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC). For some vitamins, a certain similarity in physical properties and physiological effects on the body has also been established.

Until now, the classification of vitamins was based on their solubility in water or fats. Based on solubility, vitamins are divided into

- *water-soluble* - C and B vitamins .
- *fat-soluble vitamins (lipovitamins)* - A, D, E , K,

Water-soluble vitamins include: B vitamins: B1 (thiamine, aneurin), B2 (riboflavin), PP (nicotinic acid, nicotinamide), B6 (pyridoxine, pyridoxal, pyridoxamine), B12 (cyanocobalamin); folic acid (folacin, pteroi glutamic acid); pantothenic acid; biotin (vitamin H); C (ascorbic acid).

Fat-soluble vitamins accumulate in the body, and the place of their accumulation is adipose tissue and liver. Water-soluble vitamins are not stored in significant quantities and, if in excess, are excreted in the urine. This explains the high prevalence of hypovitaminosis of water-soluble vitamins and hypervitaminosis of fat-soluble vitamins.

A high metabolic rate in children, which not only supports life, but also ensures the growth and development of the child's body, requires sufficient and regular intake of not only vitamins, but also macro- and microelements. According to some scientists, the use of vitamin and mineral complexes is relevant for children and adolescents. Only about half of multivitamin preparations meet the daily intake requirements for vitamins.

The vast majority of people need to take vitamin supplements. For example, the main source of vitamin D in the human body is its formation in the skin during tanning, but not intake with food. However, there are mutations due to which skin cells are unable to produce vitamin D even with excess sunlight, such people need medicinal support for the level of this vitamin. It is preferable to replenish the lack of vitamins from food products (fruits, vegetables), and not from pharmaceutical drugs. In most cases, the best way to provide the body with vitamins and other essential substances is a healthy diet based on choosing products with the greatest nutritional value in their most natural form.

Vitamins, while playing a huge role in metabolism, are not a source of energy for the body (since they do not have caloric value) or structural components of tissues.

Currently, 13 vitamins are known: vitamin A, B vitamins (B₁, B₂, B₃, B₅, B₆, B₇, B₉, B₁₂), vitamin D, vitamin C, vitamin E, vitamin K, vitamin PP.

The human body synthesizes vitamin D (under the influence of ultraviolet radiation), vitamin A (synthesized from precursors that enter the body with food) and one of the forms of vitamin B₃ - niacin (synthesized from a precursor - the amino acid tryptophan). Also, thanks to the normal microflora of the large intestine, vitamins K and B₇ are synthesized in sufficient quantities. The main source of vitamins is food.

Fat-soluble vitamins

Vitamins of this class include vitamins A, D, E, K.

Vitamin A – retinol belongs to the group of carotene derivatives.

The most important of these are *retinol* and its esters with acetic (retinol acetate) and palmitic acids (retinyl palmitate) and retinoic acid.

The functions of vitamin A in the body can be divided into two groups:

- participation in photoreception and perception of light;
- growth, reproduction, proliferation of cells.

The normal level of vitamin A in the blood is 30-70 mcg / 100 ml. Low blood retinol levels of 20 mcg / 100 ml indicate insufficient supply of vitamin A to the body. *Deficiency - hypovitaminosis* associated with vitamin A: disorders of adaptation to darkness, growth retardation, follicular hyperkeratosis, drying of mucous membranes, reproductive dysfunction.

The foods richest in vitamin A are: fish oil, eggs, butter, sour cream, animal and fish liver; plants rich in carotenoids - carrots, sorrel, spinach, green onions, sea buckthorn, black currants, blueberries, rose hips, apricots, tomatoes, peppers, peaches, strawberries and other vegetables and fruits.

Daily requirement : 1-2.5 mg of vitamin A. One IU is equivalent to 0.6 mcg of carotene and 0.3 mcg of vitamin A.

Vitamin D - calciferol, an antirachitic vitamin.

Vitamin D is a general name for a group of biologically active substances – fat-soluble vitamins D₁, D₂, D₃, D₄, D₅, D₆.

The main function of vitamin D₃ in the body is to maintain calcium and phosphorus homeostasis, ensure mineralization and regeneration of bones and teeth.

With proper consumption of vitamin D₃, bones and muscles are strengthened, blood composition improves, dry hair and skin disappear, the risk of developing cancer and diabetes is reduced, immunity, performance, concentration are increased, the thyroid gland and heart function are improved, and blood pressure is regulated.

Vitamin D deficiency – a very common problem in Uzbekistan, since most of our territory is in the zone of low insolation (solar radiation exposure). Vitamin D₃ is synthesized by the body only if the sun's rays hit the skin at a certain angle, which is observed from 11 a.m. to 2 p.m.

Vitamin D₃ deficiency in adults leads to fatigue, irritability, sleep disorders, decreased vision, loss of bone mass and brittle bones, as well as aching pain in the bones and joints, increased sweating in the occipital region, cramps, pulling pain in the muscles, dry, peeling skin, frequent respiratory infections.

Symptoms of deficiency in children: in childhood, when the child's skeleton, teeth and muscular body are actively forming, an adequate level of vitamin D is very important. Among the symptoms of deficiency of this vitamin in children are: increased tearfulness, excitability and sleep disturbances, growth retardation, slow closure of the fontanelle, weight loss, profuse sweating, especially during sleep, rickets, changes in the skeletal system (bent legs, enlarged head, flat back of the head, too convex forehead).

The foods richest in vitamin D are fish oil, sour cream, liver, egg yolk, fish, cereals, milk, butter, and cheese.

The daily requirement for vitamin D in children is 12-25 mcg, and in adults - less.

Vitamin E is a whole group of biologically active substances: tocopherols and tocotrienols. To distinguish them, each is assigned a Greek letter: alpha, beta, gamma and delta. Alpha and delta-tocopherols have the greatest activity. They are found mainly in products of plant origin, as a rule, in those with a lot of vegetable fat.

Results and discussion. Therefore, all vegetable oils are the best source of vitamin E. The functions of vitamin E in the body are varied. First of all, it is a powerful antioxidant. It helps restore cell membranes and protects tissues from the effects of free radicals that destroy body cells. Scientists consider the antioxidant properties of vitamin E as one of the means of preventing cancer. Vitamin E improves the nutrition of the skin and hair, reduces their dryness, and strengthens nails. Due to this property, it is included in the composition of therapeutic and preventive cosmetics and it is recommended to consume products rich in it for skin diseases. Vitamin E affects blood clotting, helping to prevent the formation of blood clots, improves the elasticity of large and small vessels, and slows down the formation of cholesterol plaques. In addition, this vitamin is vital for the normal functioning of the reproductive system.

Vitamin E helps improve sperm production in men, and in women it is involved in the regulation of the menstrual cycle and alleviates unpleasant symptoms during menopause. Vitamin E is important for the proper nutrition of the embryo - it improves the absorption of nutrients by cells. Vitamin E also regulates energy metabolism in muscles, helping to accumulate energy reserves - glycogen. It improves the functioning of the nervous system and strengthens the immune system, also promotes the absorption of nutrients, including vitamin D, and protects vitamin A from destruction in the body. That is why vitamins A and E are called partners. Vitamin E is exposed to atmospheric oxygen and ultraviolet radiation. It is formed only in the green part of plants, especially in cereals. They are rich in vegetable oils. Animal products contain few tocopherols.

Vitamin E deficiency increases the susceptibility of red blood cells to peroxide hemolysis; testicular atrophy, fetal absorption during pregnancy; muscular dystrophy, liver necrosis, softening of brain components, especially the cerebrum. Decreases the sensitivity of membrane receptors to hormones.

Signs of deficiency: degenerative changes in skeletal muscles, myocardium, hypotrophy, gait disturbances, paresis of the oculomotor muscles, increased permeability and fragility of capillaries, impaired spermatogenesis and oogenesis, impaired placental development, increased incidence of spontaneous abortions. Blood composition disorders in children, early birth, anemia, edema.

Foods rich in vitamin E: vegetable oils (mostly unrefined), avocado, nuts, wheat germ, tomatoes, grains and legumes, liver, egg yolk. Daily requirement 5-10 mg of the body.

Vitamin E is the main representative of the antioxidant group. It has a rejuvenating effect, slowing down the aging of cells caused by the harmful effects of free radicals on the body's cells. The effect of vitamin E on the body is difficult to overestimate: it prevents aging, increases the body's defenses, improves the functioning of the sex and other endocrine glands, helps with erectile dysfunction in men and with threatened abortions in women, acting together with vitamin A, it protects the lungs from the effects of polluted air, accelerates the healing of burns.

It is necessary for the normal functioning of muscles and the nervous system, improves heart function, stimulates blood circulation and the formation of red blood cells, prevents the formation of blood clots, promotes natural thermoregulation of the body, increases immunity in old age and prevents the development of cataracts and muscle atrophy, protects cells from the aggressive effects of X-rays, ultraviolet radiation (solar and artificial), chemicals (in food and water).

Vitamin K

Vitamin K unites a group of various derivatives of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone with side chains. All of them are insoluble in water and dissolve well in organic solvents. They are easily oxidized by atmospheric oxygen. Vitamin K is mainly found in green plants, especially cabbage. There is little vitamin K in animal products. For example, pork liver contains 0.4-0.8 $\mu\text{g} / \text{g}$.

Vitamin K is synthesized by normal microflora of the human intestine. In the blood, the vitamin binds to albumin, enters organs and tissues, where it takes active forms. It accumulates in the liver, spleen and heart and is excreted in the urine.

Vitamin K is involved in the synthesis of membrane phospholipids, glycoproteins, lipoproteins and an important phospholipid of the nerve cell - sphingosine. It has a positive effect on the termination of free radical reactions and the adhesion of peroxides to membranes. When tissues are exposed to light, vitamin K helps maintain membrane balance and, like vitamin E, increases the sensitivity of membranes to hormone receptors. The main biological significance of vitamin K is that it is involved in the synthesis of proteins that promote blood clotting in the liver. In this process, vitamin K is involved as a coenzyme in the carboxylation reactions of glutamic acid residues in protein molecules, including the formation of prothrombin from preprothrombin. Vitamin K deficiency slows down blood clotting, which leads to bleeding and the development of hemorrhagic symptoms. Carboxylation Glutamic acid depends not only on the amount of vitamin K, but also on the amount of phospholipids in the membranes. Vitamin K prevents infection from entering the blood.

Symptoms of deficiency: poor blood clotting, inactive liver.

Overdose: jaundice, anemia.

Foods rich in vitamin K : all types of cabbage, beets, green plants.

The daily requirement of the body is 1–2 mg .

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